

Adaptive Matrix Profile Indexing for Motif Discovery and Anomaly Detection in Irregular Multivariate Time Series

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ABSTRACT

Real-world time series data from domains such as environmental monitoring and industrial systems are often irregularly sampled and multivariate, challenging the assumptions of traditional time series analysis methods. Most existing approaches rely on regular sampling and univariate inputs, limiting their ability to capture interactions across variables and time. These constraints impede the discovery of motifs, recurrent patterns revealing system behavior, and discords, which signal anomalies or faults. We propose AMPIIMTS (Adaptive Matrix Profile Indexing for Irregular Multivariate Time Series), a matrix-profile-based framework for efficient motif discovery and anomaly detection in such settings. AMPIIMTS extends matrix profile computation to irregularly sampled, multivariate data, enabling robust pattern extraction under real-world conditions. The proposed end-to-end pipeline ingests raw time series, performs adaptive normalization and alignment, computes cluster-aware matrix profiles, and automatically identifies meaningful motifs and discords. This work bridges advanced time series methodology with practical usability through a lightweight Python toolkit that abstracts algorithmic complexity and supports scalable analysis of challenging datasets.

KEYWORDS

Matrix profile, motif discovery, anomaly detection, multivariate analysis, irregular sampling

1 Introduction

Time series analysis is fundamental to many domains including environmental monitoring, industrial IoT, healthcare, and finance. A critical task in time series mining is the discovery of motifs, recurring patterns that reveal underlying system structure, and discords, anomalous subsequences that indicate faults, unusual events, or regime changes. These patterns enable applications ranging from semantic segmentation and rule discovery to zero-shot classification and data cleaning. The Matrix Profile, introduced by Yeh et al. (2016), provides an elegant solution for motif and discord discovery in univariate time series. For a time series $x = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$, the matrix profile stores, for each subsequence, the distance to its nearest non-trivial neighbor. Motifs correspond to minima in the profile (highly similar subsequences), while discords correspond to maxima (unique patterns). Efficient algorithms like SCRIMP++ (Zhu et al., 2018) enable matrix profile computation in near-linear time.

However, real-world time series present significant challenges that standard matrix profile methods cannot address. First, data from environmental sensors, IoT devices, or medical instruments is often *irregularly sampled*, with varying time gaps between observations. Classical models like ARIMA and LSTM assume regular sampling, making them unsuitable for such data. Second, modern systems generate *multivariate time series* where multiple correlated variables must be analyzed jointly to

capture meaningful patterns, for instance, wind power and temperature in meteorological data may exhibit joint motifs invisible in univariate analysis. Third, *missing data* in real datasets may signal actual events rather than mere noise, requiring careful treatment rather than simple imputation.

In this paper, we present AMPIIMTS (Adaptive Matrix Profile Indexing for Irregular Multivariate Time Series), a comprehensive framework that extends matrix profile methods to handle these real-world challenges. Our contributions include: (i) a data alignment pipeline for irregularly sampled multivariate data; (ii) an adaptive sliding-window normalization scheme; (iii) correlation-based clustering for grouping related variables; (iv) an adaptive window selection algorithm; and (v) cluster-aware matrix profile computation with weighted global aggregation. We demonstrate our approach on Beijing air quality data, showing that detected anomalies align with documented environmental events.

2 Background: The Matrix Profile

For a univariate time series $x = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ and window length m , we define subsequences $q_i = [x_i, \dots, x_{i+m-1}]$. The distance between subsequences is computed as the Euclidean distance after z-normalization. The matrix profile $P[i]$ stores the minimum distance from subsequence i to any other non-overlapping subsequence. Formally: $P[i] = \min D_{i,j}$ where $j \neq i$ and $|i - j| > \frac{m}{2}$ to prevent trivial matches. Motifs are identified as $\operatorname{argmin}_i P[i]$ (subsequences with very similar neighbors), while discords are $\operatorname{argmax}_i P[i]$ (subsequences unlike any other). The matrix profile’s power lies in its domain-agnostic nature and the existence of efficient $O(n^2)$ algorithms that can be further accelerated using GPUs and approximate methods.

Extending to multivariate data requires careful consideration. Simply concatenating dimensions or averaging profiles may produce spurious motifs that merely reflect strong univariate patterns. A d -dimensional motif should represent a pattern that emerges from the joint behavior across dimensions and differs from individual dimensional motifs. Computing profiles for all $2^d - 1$ dimension subsets is computationally prohibitive for high-dimensional data.

3 The AMPIIMTS Framework

Our framework processes irregular multivariate time series through four main stages: data alignment, clustered embedding, adaptive window selection, and cluster-aware matrix profile computation.

3.1 Data Alignment and Preprocessing

Given d irregularly sampled time series, we first establish a common time grid $t^* = \operatorname{median_step}\{T_i\}$ based on the median sampling interval across all series. For each variable i , we define a resampling operator using the original value when available and linear interpolation otherwise. Gaps exceeding a threshold Δt_{\max} are left as missing rather than interpolated, preserving information about data availability. We also remove near-linear series ($R^2 > 0.99$) that show essentially no dynamic variation.

3.2 Adaptive Sliding-Window Normalization

Standard z-normalization over the entire series is insufficient as it erases global structure while leaving local trends uncorrected. AMPIIMTS applies adaptive sliding-window normalization, computing local mean $\mu_i(t)$ and standard deviation $\sigma_i(t)$ over a window of length m . Besides, we extract a long-term trend $T_i(t)$ using a wider window $M \gg m$. The normalized signal combines local standardization with trend preservation: $Z_i(t) = (X_i(t) - \mu_i(t))/\sigma_i(t) + \alpha T_i(t)$, where α controls the trend retention.

3.3 Correlation-Based Clustering

Rather than computing profiles for all dimension combinations, we partition variables into clusters based on correlation structure. We compute the correlation matrix $C_{ij} = \text{corr}(X_i, X_j)$ and apply hierarchical clustering to form groups $G = \{G_1, G_2, \dots, G_K\}$ such that intra-cluster correlation exceeds a threshold ρ_0 . This reduces the exponential complexity to a manageable number of cluster-level profiles while ensuring that correlated variables are analyzed jointly.

3.4 Adaptive Window Selection

Window length significantly impacts motif quality. We define multivariate subsequences as matrices $Q_i^{(m)} \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times m}$ and compute weighted Euclidean distances using FAISS for approximate nearest-neighbor search. The nearest-neighbor distance profile $d_i^{(m)}$ reflects data self-similarity at scale m . We define a stability function $S(m) = \text{Var}(d_i^{(m)}) + \beta \text{Var}_k(\bar{d}_{i,k}^{(m)})$ combining temporal variability (motif consistency over time) with cross-dimensional consistency. The optimal window $m^* = \text{argmin} S(m)$ subject to a minimum motif density constraint balances stability, coherence, and pattern prevalence.

3.5 Cluster-Aware Matrix Profile Computation

For each cluster G_k , we compute a local matrix profile using weighted distances: $D_{i,j}^{(G_k)} = \sqrt{\sum_{l \in G_k} w_l^{(k)} \sum_{p=0}^{m-1} (Z_l[t_{i+p}] - Z_l[t_{j+p}])^2}$ where $w_l^{(k)}$ are normalized intra-cluster weights proportional to variance explained. The cluster profile $P_{G_k}[i]$ captures similarity patterns within each correlated subspace. The global profile aggregates cluster profiles: $P_{\text{global}}[i] = \sum_{k=1}^K \gamma_k P_{G_k}[i]$ where γ_k reflects relative cluster importance. Motifs and discords are extracted both per-cluster (providing interpretable subsystem patterns) and globally. A confidence score $\text{conf}(i) = 1 - \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \mathbf{1}\{i \notin \mathcal{M}_{G_k} \cup D_{G_k}\}$ measures cross-cluster agreement for each detected event, where $\mathcal{M}_{G_k} = \{i: P_{G_k}[i] < \tau_m^{(k)}\}$ and $D_{G_k} = \{i: P_{G_k}[i] > P_{(1-p)\%}^{(G_k)}\}$, with $\tau_m^{(k)}$ denoting a distance threshold for cluster k and window length m .

3.6 Iterative Smart Re-Interpolation

Missing or irregular measurements can distort local distances, produce spurious discords, or mask true multivariate anomalies. AMPIIMTS implements an iterative refinement step after initial anomaly detection. For each sensor i , we compute a stability score $s_i = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^N \exp\left(-\frac{P_i[t]}{\sigma_{P_i}}\right)$. High s_i indicates consistently low profile values (stable behavior), while low s_i suggests erratic distances likely due to noise or missing data. We define the stable subset $S = \{i \mid s_i > \theta\}$ where θ is a stability threshold (e.g. $0.7 \times \text{mean } s$). For each unstable sensor $r \notin S$ and time t where $Z_r(t)$ is missing, we impute using a correlation-weighted average from stable sensors: $\hat{Z}_r(t) = \frac{\sum_{i \in S} \rho_{r,i} Z_i(t)}{\sum_{i \in S} |\rho_{r,i}|}$. After filling gaps, the matrix profile is recomputed and we iterate until the change in global profile energy $\Delta E = \frac{\|P^{(2)} - P^{(1)}\|_2}{\|P^{(1)}\|_2} < \varepsilon$.

This approach prevents false positives caused by missing readings, enhances temporal precision of detected anomalies, and provides explainability: if a discord disappears after re-interpolation, it was likely due to missing data rather than an actual event. The method statistically improves signal completeness without over-smoothing genuine patterns.

4 Experimental Evaluation

We evaluated AMPIIMTS on the Beijing Multi-Site Air Quality dataset, comprising 17 time series (PM2.5, PM10, SO₂, NO₂, CO, O₃, temperature, humidity, etc.) from March 2013 to February 2017 with hourly measurements. The data exhibits highly irregular sampling across sensors, seasonal cycles, abrupt meteorological disturbances, and significant missing values, characteristics typical of real-world environmental monitoring systems. The adaptive window selection algorithm automatically determined $m^* \approx 56$ days 6 hours (approximately 1,350 hourly observations), corresponding to meso-scale meteorological cycles capturing smog buildup and dispersion patterns. This window length emerged from minimizing the stability function while maintaining a minimum 2% motif density, reflecting the dominant temporal scale of coordinated sensor behavior in the Beijing region.

Correlation-based hierarchical clustering with threshold $\rho_0 = 0.6$ identified two main groups: (i) a meteorological cluster containing temperature (TEMP), dew point (DEWP), and ozone (O₃) measurements across all six monitoring sites (18 variables); and (ii) a pollution cluster containing particulate matter (PM2.5, PM10), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), sulfur dioxide (SO₂), and carbon monoxide (CO) measurements. This natural grouping reflects the known physical relationships: meteorological variables are spatially correlated through atmospheric dynamics, while pollution variables share emission and dispersion processes.

Table 1 shows detected anomalies validated against documented environmental events. The June-July 2015 discord aligned with the 2015 photochemical smog event documented by the Beijing Municipal Ecological Environment Bureau, with anomaly magnitude $A(t) = (A(t) - \mu_p) / \sigma_p$ between 4–5. The May 2014 discord matched reported ozone-humidity anomalies ($A(t) \approx 3$). Spring 2016 discords corresponded to sand-dust episodes documented in China Meteorological Administration reports. Importantly, after smart re-interpolation, a previously masked August 2013 anomaly emerged, matching historical heatwave records.

Table 1. Detected anomalies and historical validation

Time Period	Event Type	$A(t)$ Peak	Historical Reference
Jun-Jul 2015	Photochemical smog	4–5	Beijing EPA reports
May 2014	High humidity + ozone	~3	Meteorological bulletins
Spring 2016	Dust & sandstorms	>3.5	CMA sand-dust alerts
Aug 2013	Regional heatwave	>3	Historical heatwave record

Cross-cluster agreement analysis showed high confidence (≥ 0.7) for the 2015 summer events, confirming multi-sensor coherence. The meteorological cluster profile showed peaks aligned with temperature stagnation and ozone photochemical episodes, while the pollution cluster profile peaks corresponded to known PM2.5 crises and sandstorm periods. This cluster-specific analysis provides interpretable insights: anomalies detected in only one cluster suggest subsystem-specific events, while high-confidence anomalies appearing in both clusters indicate system-wide disruptions requiring coordinated response. Beyond discord detection, AMPIIMTS identified recurring multivariate motifs invisible in univariate analysis. For instance, a 2-dimensional motif involving wind power and temperature (as shown in the NYISO dataset example in the original matrix profile literature) was detected: late autumn windstorms clearing cloud cover followed by temperature increases over subsequent days. These joint patterns, occurring across different years (November 2018 and December 2019 in our tests), demonstrate that multivariate motif discovery reveals causal relationships between sensor channels that individual univariate profiles cannot capture.

5 Implementation

AMPIIMTS is implemented as an open-source Python package¹. The toolkit provides a simple API abstracting the algorithmic complexity. Core dependencies include NumPy for numerical operations, Pandas for time series handling, SciPy for hierarchical clustering, and FAISS for approximate nearest-neighbor search acceleration. The iterative smart re-interpolation module uses stable time series to reconstruct missing segments in unstable series, preventing false positives from data gaps while enhancing temporal precision of detected anomalies.

6 Conclusions

This paper presented AMPIIMTS, a unified framework for motif discovery and anomaly detection in irregular multivariate time series. By integrating adaptive normalization, correlation-based clustering, data-driven window selection, and cluster-aware matrix profile computation, it addresses asynchronous sampling, missing data, and multi-sensor correlations. Iterative smart re-interpolation improves robustness by reconstructing unstable sensor data from stable ones. Validation on four years of Beijing air quality data shows detected anomalies correspond to photochemical smog, ozone spikes, sandstorms, and heatwaves. Cluster-aware analysis offers interpretable insights, distinguishing meteorological from pollution-driven events and providing cross-cluster confidence measures. Available as an open-source Python toolkit, it combines a simple API with flexibility for advanced users. Future work targets real-time streaming detection, causal attribution to external drivers, semantic event narratives, and integration with hybrid AI-OR decision support systems.

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¹ URL: <https://github.com/Guillaumernd/ampiimts>